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360-DEGREE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL: A MYTH OR A FACT

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Abstract

Nothing shapes our lives as much as the questions we ask-Sam keen. The shape can be in any form, and one such shape is in the form of 360-degree performance appraisals carried out in an organization.

This research paper will give more rounded diagnosis of development needs resulting in more effective development plans for individuals and more strategically focussed investment for the organization as a whole. It will give a peep into the importance of 360-degree and why 360-degree performance appraisals are the need of the hour, stressing it as a fact rather than a myth.

Key words: 360-degree performance appraisals, myth, diagnosis.

Introduction:

360-degree feedback is sometimes adage as “Multi-source assessment” or multi-rather feedback. It refers to an individual figuratively at the centre of the circle.

360-degree had its genesis way back in 1950’s at “ESSO research and Engineering Company”. Where it was used to gather information about employees and reconciled in the form of multi-rather feedback.

360-degree is a simple guide for introducing appraisals in an organization.

Performance appraisals are not play-safe gimmicks as the tag should be attached as “handle with care”. If not handled with precision the damages are far reaching.

360-degree being a part of performance appraisals is a developmental tool that helps employees recognize strengths and weaknesses and become more effective .It tries to measure behaviour and competencies and how other perceive an employee, addresses skills such as listening, planning and goal- setting. Focuses on subjective areas such as team work, character and leadership effectiveness. Planning and logistical considerations have to be kept in mind to avoid Gridlock! Every feedback should be anywhere from 10-14 days.

360-degree mechanism a myth/fact:

360-degree mechanism is not a myth rather than a fact in an organization, whose importance can be gauged from the very fact is revealed in the from different surveys carried out from time to time.

Andersons survey reveals (1997) that 20% of the organization uses the 360-degree method as a part of performance appraisals. Talents, behavioural Quirks, values, ethical standards and tempers are evaluated as being a potential weapon in the hands of the manager.

IPD survey (1998) reveals that organization at a large (51%) used 360-degree as a Quiet essential rather feedback to increase awareness and employee participation in leadership development and work unit effectiveness.

Armstrong considers 360-degree feedback methodology to cover Questionnaire ratings, data processing and follow up action. A simple 360-degree feedback profile is as depicted in the diagram below:-

Gives useful feedback Establishes good Working relations Is open to new ideas Values other opinions Recognizes achievements
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The performance management group survey (1997), reported the following benefits resulting from the use of 360-degree feedback.

1. Individuals get a broader perspective of how others perceive them.
2. Increased awareness of and relevance of competencies.
3. Increased awareness by senior management that they too have developmental needs.
4. More reliable feedback.
5. Acceptance of perceptions of multiple atake holders as a measure of performance.
6. Encourages open feedback that provides new insights.
7. Provides a clear picture to senior management of their managee’s real worth.
8. Identifies organizations strengths and weakness.
9. Raises self awareness.

10. Focus on agenda for development and compels managers to discuss developmental issues.

Multi source assessment is an assessment made from all directions as can be interpreted from the diagram below:

This is basically done to bring about a strong stimulus for individual change along with sound administrative decisions about individuals.

According to Geak, Farrell and oliver (1998) 41% of human resource and personnel professionals in UK use 360-degree feedback inn their organizations and almost 3(three) quarters plan to extend their use.

When decided on a 360-degree performance appraisals system, pilot it with a few people to launch it through seminars or workshops including role plays and demonstrations.

The necessity of 360-degree performance appraisal can be gauged from the following points. To plan develop and implement 360-degree feedback the methodology should focus on the following points.

1. Define objectives in a clear cut manner because relationships, climate ever performance is at stake.
2. Decision on giving the charge and challenge of feedback.
3. Feedback gathering has to be well defined in terms of its dimensions i.e. performance, behaviour or competencies who should be given the responsibility, as this is a very important aspect.
4. Method of gathering the feedback – e.g. Pilot questionnaire.
5. Data analysis and presentations.
6. Planning the initial implementation small wins are important. The pilot schema must be meticulous with planning and preparation, awareness, generation etc.
7. Analysis of outcomes of pilot scheme. They are a part of learning process.
8. Monitor and evaluate.
9. Dysfunctional anxiety and stress are common and 360-degree feedback is a special component of feedback monitoring and evaluation.
10. Last but not the least every step should have the precessions as the person and the organization is at a stake.

CONCLUSION

In the end it can only be said that 360-degree is a feedback mechanism which has to care of certain areas, making feedback and endeavour to develop and not to demolish, giving feedback with care, stressing the positives and being more sensitive and trustworthy. Communicating clearly and timing it well.

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